

THE IMPORTANCE OF MORAL EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The values that ensure the existence of man and society are gradually passed from ancestors to generations due to national education. The term national education is used in broad and narrow senses.

It is known that the general social task of education is to form knowledge, skills, social experience and moral standards in the young generation. Accordingly, education of the young generation implies goal-oriented educational influence, creation of necessary conditions regarding the norms of interaction in social life and the requirements to comply with it.

It is known from history that the Uzbek people have rich spiritual and cultural values. Through these values, traditions, customs and methods of education, our grandfathers and grandmothers brought up their children with good manners. Children brought up in the spirit of national values gained a reputation for intelligence, kindness, patriotism, courage and bravery.

Our people experienced the European way of life in the following years. Western culture has replaced several thousand-year-old traditions, customs, traditions and methods of national education. They were sometimes instilled through oppression. As a result, our nation has become equal to the rich cultural and spiritual heritage and family upbringing methods formed historically.

In our opinion, such a situation has a negative effect on the effectiveness of education in Uzbek families today, reducing the role of influence of family education. As a result, the relationship between parents and children became strained. In families, kindness, respect for children, and respect for elders decreased. This eventually began to affect the environment and society. That's probably why the behavior of young people in public places today sometimes makes people angry.

In recent times, significant works are being carried out in the socio-economic, political,

spiritual-educational, cultural spheres in Uzbekistan. All of this is based on comprehensive protection of human rights, citizens of our country and youth.

In our country, 1997 is called "Year of Human Interests", 1998 is "Year of Family", 2001 is "Year of Healthy Generation", 2008 is "Year of Youth", 2010 is "Year of Healthy Generation" and the adoption and implementation of State programs on this. is also a proof of our opinion above.

President Shavkat Mirziyoev said, "It is known that education of the young generation has always been important and relevant. But in the 21st century we live in, this issue is really becoming a matter of life and death. "The more perfect the education, the happier the people," say the sages. In order for the education to be perfect, it is absolutely impossible to allow a gap to appear in this matter" is a proof that special attention is paid to the education of young people in our country.

The values that ensure the existence of man and society are gradually passed from ancestors to generations due to national education. The term national education is used in broad and narrow senses. In a broad sense, it means the totality of all spiritual influences, activities, actions, and aspirations aimed at forming a human personality, ensuring his active participation in production and social, cultural, and educational life. National education in this understanding. it includes not only the educational work carried out in the family, school, children and youth organizations, but also the entire social system, its leading ideas, literature, art, cinema, radio, TV, mass media, etc.

Also, national education in a broad sense includes education and information in this field. In a narrow sense, national education means a pedagogical activity aimed at cultivating the spiritual development, worldview, moral image, and aesthetic taste of a particular person. This is done by family and educational institutions and public organizations.

As we know, any upbringing exists only in close connection with education. Because, in the process of education and information acquisition, not only the knowledge of a person increases, but also the determination of spiritual and moral qualities is accelerated. It is for this reason that our forefathers considered knowledge, education and training to be the most important condition and guarantee of human perfection and nation's development.

At the same time, this is a national issue that requires the participation and support of the general public, the whole nation... When I think about it, I remember Abdulla Awlani's words "Education is a matter of life or death, salvation or destruction, happiness or disaster for us. I remember his deep meaning words. These words of our great enlightened grandfather were as important and relevant for our nation at the beginning of our century, they are as important and relevant for us now.

PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", PF-60 dated March 7, 2022 Ensuring the implementation of Decree No. 87 and Decision No. PQ-322 dated July 14, 2022 "On additional measures for the further development of public-private partnership in the field of preschool education",

Also, in accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 129 dated February 24, 2022 "On the organization of the activities of the State Financial Control Inspectorate under the Ministry of Finance and measures to improve financial control in budget organizations" in order to further improve the processes of public-private partnership in the field of preschool

education, the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers we is being programmed for.

As can be seen from the above points, national education is of crucial importance in the life of any society and country. Because, for its growth and development, the production of material and spiritual wealth must increase continuously. For this, the young generation needs to rise to a higher level than their ancestors in creating these assets. It is especially necessary to implement the recommendations of modern medicine, pedagogy, and psychology in every family to properly educate young people both physically and spiritually.

It is extremely important for every family, parents, first of all, to see a person in the form of a child, and to always feel that they are responsible for providing all the rights and freedoms that belong to the person.

Each of the emblems and symbols that serve the national idea and national pride in national education is a great textbook and a powerful educational tool. In addition, celebrating the birth dates of great ancestors also has spiritual and historical significance.

In addition, celebrating the birth dates of great ancestors also has spiritual and historical significance. By conducting such ceremonies, young people are brought up on the basis of new values, they are instilled in their hearts to understand and value history, to approach the past with respect, to preserve it, and to be proud of belonging to this nation.

In general, the ethnic image of the youth is formed through the dialectical interaction of the nation's current national upbringing, mentality, and culture. A person who has received a good spiritual education lives consciously with his own mind, his own thinking, his own work, his own responsibilities, as a free and free-thinking person.

References:

1. Decision No. 426 of the Cabinet of Ministers, Tashkent, August 2, 2022.
2. S. Yusupova. Pedagogy of preschool education. Study guide — T.: "Teacher". 1993
3. N. Ochilova. THE MAIN FEATURES OF WESTERN EUROPE MEDIEVAL, MODERN PHILOSOPHY AND PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS IN THE 9TH-12TH CENTURIES IN CENTRAL ASIA. Journal of Critical Reviews . ISSN- 2394-5125. Vol 7, Issue 14, 2020. 193-199. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.14.34>
4. N. Ochilova . East And West: Integration And Cooperation In The Process Of Globalization. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 2020.2(11),543-546.
5. N. Ochilova. The role of aesthetics in shaping the young generation. Multidisciplinary Research SJIF Impact Factor :5.614 ISI I.F. Monthly Peer Reviewed & Indexed International Online Journal March 2020. 123-125
6. N. Ochilova. The importance of understanding national identity in Education of the young neighboring. «SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS» Scientific Journal ISSN: 2181-1601//Volume:1,ISSUE:6 APRIL 2021. 209-214. www.scientificprogress.uz
7. N. Ochilova. Problems of science № 3 (62), 2021 Russian impact factor: 0.17 Scientific methodical magazine. ISSN 2413-2101 (Print) ISSN 2542-078X Online) Moscow 2021. 37-41
8. N. Ochilova. The Role of Aesthetics in Shaping the Younger Generation . International Journal of Academic Management Science Research (IJAMSR) ISSN: 2643-900X Vol. 5 Issue 2, February - 2021, Pages: 102-103. The Research Paper is Original and Innovative. It is Peer-Reviewed. Washington DC, USA <http://www.ijeais.org/ijamsr> ijamsreditor@gmail.com
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